

Accomplishments and Media Coverage of Nepal's First Elected Government

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Abstract:

This article examines the work and impact of Nepal's first elected government following the 2007 revolution, which ended 104 years of family Rana rule and established democracy in the country. The revolution set the stage for a transition to a political system based on multi-party democracy and constitutional monarchy. Initially, King Tribhuvan promised to advance the country through a constitution created by representatives elected to a Constituent Assembly within two years. However, both King Tribhuvan and his successor, King Mahendra, avoided holding the Constituent Assembly elections out

of fear that an elected body might challenge the monarchy. The kings repeatedly postponed the elections while maneuvering to preserve their power. Eventually, political pressure led to the acceptance of parliamentary elections in 2015, with even the republican communist party being coerced into recognizing the monarchy. King Mahendra, however, only agreed to the elections after ensuring no single party could dominate the state machinery. Contrary to the king's expectations, the Nepali Congress achieved a two-thirds majority in the 2015 general election. Once in power, the elected government began efforts to promote public welfare. In response, the king intervened by using military force to dissolve the parliament and suspend the government for 18 months, preventing them from functioning effectively for five years. During this period, political parties were banned, and newspapers critical of the royal actions were censored. This article highlights the significant achievements and challenges faced by Nepal's first elected government, as well as the broader implications of the royal intervention on the country's democratic processes.

Keywords: *Parliament, first elected government, King Mahendra, democracy, monarchy, freedom of the press.*

Introduction

The 1950 people's revolution in Nepal marked the end of a 104-year autocratic Rana regime and paved the way for democracy. Following this

significant shift, Nepal conducted its first parliamentary general elections in 1959. This election process, which commenced on February 18, 1949 and concluded on April 10, was notably protracted, with results from the various

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stages taking 45 days to be fully announced. Out of a total electorate of 4.25 million, 1.98 million voters participated. The elections featured 786 candidates, including 518 from nine political parties and 268 independents (Banarasi, 2015: 27). The Nepali Congress emerged victorious, securing a two-thirds majority with 74 seats and 37.2% of the vote. The Gorkha Parishad won 19 seats with 17.03%, while the Nepal Communist Party, United Democratic Party, Nepal People's Council, and independent members filled the remaining seats (Nepal, 2016). Despite this clear electoral outcome, the King did not immediately invite the Nepali Congress to form a new government. For two months after the election results were announced, no progress was made in government formation. When the elected parliament was eventually convened, the King enacted a law enhancing the privileges of the monarchy and reasserted control over the army. It was not until December 15, 1960, that BP Koirala, leader of the Nepali Congress parliamentary party, was appointed as Prime Minister, thus establishing the first elected government (Pande, Annapurna 2019, April 27).

In Nepal, a small South Asian nation grappling with severe poverty, illiteracy, and unemployment, the introduction of a multi-party system was anticipated to accelerate progress significantly. However, the hope for rapid development was short-lived. The King dissolved the parliament and government shortly after their formation, reverting to autocratic rule. Prime Minister BP Koirala and his ministers were imprisoned, and essential democratic institutions such as political parties, civil liberties, and press freedom were dismantled. This led to a 30-year period of autocratic rule, halting the democratic advancements that had begun with the revolution.

Statement of the Problem

The 2007 revolution in Nepal, which ended a 104-year autocratic Rana regime, was a watershed moment in the country's political history, marking a shift towards democracy and a multi-party system. This transition set the stage for Nepal's first parliamentary general elections in 1949, which were expected to usher in a new

era of democratic governance. However, the electoral process and subsequent government formation were fraught with challenges. King Tribhuvan and his successor, King Mahendra, delayed the Constituent Assembly elections due to fears that an elected body might challenge the monarchy. Even after political pressure led to the 1949 elections, the King's continued intervention, including dissolving the parliament and suspending the government, thwarted the democratic process.

The problem this study seeks to address is the gap in understanding regarding the accomplishments and media coverage of Nepal's first elected government. Despite the promising start, the elected government faced significant hurdles, including royal interference that curtailed its ability to govern effectively. This intervention not only impacted the government's performance but also shaped how it was perceived by the public. The media's portrayal of the government during this tumultuous period is critical to understanding the broader implications for democratic consolidation in Nepal.

The central issues to be explored include:

- The extent and nature of the accomplishments of Nepal's first elected government.
- How media coverage influenced public perception of the government's achievements and challenges.
- The impact of royal interventions on the democratic process and the effectiveness of the elected government.

This study aims to fill the existing knowledge gap by providing a detailed analysis of both the achievements of the first elected government and the media's role in shaping public opinion. Understanding these dynamics is essential for evaluating the successes and failures of Nepal's transition to democracy and for informing future democratic efforts in similar contexts.

Objectives of the Study

- To Document and Evaluate the Accomplishments of Nepal's First Elected

Government: This objective aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the achievements of Nepal's first elected government. By analyzing the government's policies, initiatives, and reforms, the study seeks to highlight both its successes and shortcomings in addressing key socio-economic issues such as poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy.

- **To Analyze Media Representation of the First Elected Government:** The study aims to investigate how various media outlets reported on the activities and performance of the first elected government. This includes examining media coverage from books, journals, and online sources to identify patterns in reporting and to understand how these portrayals influenced public perception.
- **To Assess the Impact of Media Coverage on Public Perception:** This objective focuses on understanding the relationship between media portrayals and public opinion. By evaluating how media coverage shaped the public's view of the government's effectiveness and legitimacy, the study seeks to reveal the broader implications for democratic engagement and governance.
- **To Evaluate the Role of Royal Interventions in Shaping Democratic Processes:** The study aims to explore how royal interventions, including the dissolution of parliament and suspension of the government, affected the democratic process. This includes analyzing the consequences of these actions on the stability and functionality of the elected government.
- **To Provide Insights for Future Democratic Transitions:** Based on the findings, the study aims to offer recommendations for future democratic transitions in similar contexts. By understanding the challenges faced by Nepal's first elected government and the role of media and royal interference, the study seeks to contribute to better practices and strategies for democratic consolidation. These objectives will guide the study in providing a thorough analysis of the accomplishments and media coverage of Nepal's first elected government, offering valuable insights into the complexities of

democratic transitions and the role of media in shaping governance outcomes.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research methodology, utilizing both primary and secondary sources. To explore the portrayal of Nepal's first elected government in the media and to assess the public image of this government, a comprehensive review of various sources was conducted. Primary sources include direct interviews and official documents, while secondary sources encompass articles from books, academic journals, and online publications. This research involved a detailed examination of how the media reported on the government's activities and how these reports shaped public perception. By analyzing these media sources, the study aims to uncover patterns and themes related to the government's portrayal and its impact on public opinion. Data collected from these sources was analyzed using descriptive and analytical methods. Descriptive analysis involved summarizing the content and key findings from the media reports, while analytical methods were used to interpret the underlying implications and trends. This approach allowed for a nuanced understanding of the media's role in shaping the image of the first elected government and provided insights into the broader implications of these portrayals for public perception.

Discussion and Finding

Inclusive Government in History

Upon his appointment as Prime Minister, Bishweshwar Prasad Koirala made a landmark move in Nepali governance by forming an exceptionally inclusive cabinet, the most representative in the nation's history. This cabinet marked a significant departure from the past, introducing unprecedented diversity in Nepali politics. Notably, it was the first time women were included as ministers, with Dwarikadevi Thakurani being appointed as the first female Member of Parliament (Basnet,

Himalkhabar, 2020, February 28). Thakurani took on the role of Assistant Minister of Local Autonomous Government. The cabinet's inclusivity extended to various regions and communities of Nepal. From the Terai region, Ram Narayan Mishra, Parashu Narayan Chaudhary, and Suryanathdas Yadav were appointed. The Kathmandu Valley was represented by Ganeshman Singh of the Newar community, while the mid-hills and Himalayas were covered by Meen Bahadur Gurung, Yogendraman Sherchan, Jamansingh Gurung, and Dewansingh Rai. Additionally, the eastern region was represented by Premraj Angdambe from the Limvu community (Dahal, Kantipur, 2014, March 1). This diverse cabinet underscored Koirala's commitment to broad representation and equitable governance, setting a new standard for inclusivity in Nepali politics.

Salary Reduction of Prime Minister and Minister

After securing victories in three consecutive general elections, Bishweshwar Prasad Koirala set his sights on transforming the socio-economic landscape of Nepal. His goal was to elevate the living standards of all Nepalis to a middle-class level. Recognizing the pervasive poverty across the country, particularly in remote villages, Koirala devised a strategic plan to address the needs of these underserved populations. As a symbol of his commitment to change and to demonstrate solidarity with the common people, Koirala implemented a significant reduction in the salaries of top government officials. The salary of the Prime Minister was reduced from 2,500 rupees to 1,500 rupees per month. Similarly, the Deputy Prime Minister's salary was decreased from 2,000 rupees to 1,200 rupees per month. The salaries of other ministers were also cut, with ministers' salaries reduced from 1,500 rupees to 1,000 rupees, and assistant ministers' salaries from 1,200 rupees to 800 rupees (Nepal Gazette, 1959, November 2). This salary reduction was part of a broader initiative to address the economic disparities within the country. In addition to slashing salaries, Koirala's administration made substantial cuts to the monthly expenses of the Prime Minister's

Office. Under the previous administration led by Tankprasad Acharya, the monthly expenses amounted to 18,000 rupees. Koirala's reforms reduced these expenses dramatically to 5,666 rupees per month, reflecting his commitment to frugality and efficient use of government resources (Poudel, Shilapatra, 2023, September 10). Koirala's policy of salary cuts and expense reductions were designed not only to curb government spending but also to set an example of austerity and prioritization of public welfare. By cutting these expenses, he aimed to redirect resources towards programs that would benefit the wider population, particularly those in dire economic conditions. This move was intended to convey a message of fiscal responsibility and commitment to addressing the needs of the poorest segments of society. Through these actions, Koirala sought to demonstrate his dedication to improving the lives of ordinary Nepalis and to lay the groundwork for a more equitable and inclusive society. His reforms were a clear indication of his desire to prioritize the welfare of the people over personal or administrative luxuries, marking a significant shift in the approach to governance in Nepal.

Abolition of Birta

Before 2007, land ownership in Nepal was highly concentrated among a few powerful entities. The Rana family controlled about 50% of the arable land, the royal family held 15%, and other influential groups, including Bhardars, Sardars, Qazis, Gurupurohits, and Jagidars, possessed significant portions as well (Acharya, 2011). Despite agriculture being the primary livelihood for 97% of Nepal's population, a substantial 36% of arable land was managed under a feudal system. The Nepali Congress addressed this issue in its election manifesto by pledging to abolish the Birta system, a form of feudal land ownership. This promise was realized with the passing of the Birta Abolition Bill. The House of Representatives approved the bill on October 16, 2016, and the General Assembly followed suit on October 18, 2016. The legislation marked a significant shift in land management by ending feudal land ownership and granting legal rights to farmers (Gorkhapatra, 2002, May 6).

Prime Minister Koirala played a crucial role in emphasizing the importance of this land reform. His administration aimed to ensure that farmers received legal rights over their land and to reduce the extent of land controlled by landlords. This reform was intended to democratize land ownership and empower the agricultural community, thereby addressing long-standing inequities in land distribution (Nepal, 2023). By implementing these changes, the Koirala government sought to improve the socio-economic conditions of farmers and promote a more equitable distribution of land resources. The transition away from the feudal system represented a significant step towards modernizing Nepal's land ownership policies and supporting most of the population reliant on agriculture.

Pro-Poor Schemes

Under the Rana regime, control of resources was heavily centralized in the hands of the Prime Minister and his family, with a substantial portion of tax revenue directed into the Prime Minister's fund (Sijapati, Kantipur, 2015, February 19). This period, prior to 1949, was marked by significant economic and social deficiencies, characterized by inadequate infrastructure and limited access to healthcare. Upon assuming office, Prime Minister Koirala made it a priority to address these shortcomings and improve the living standards of the impoverished. His approach focused on small-scale development projects designed to enhance rural life. Koirala recognized the urgent need to address the dire conditions faced by the rural population and emphasized the importance of tailoring government initiatives to meet the needs of the poor.

Koirala's vision encompassed a comprehensive government plan that aimed to provide essential services and support to underserved communities. He championed the idea that development efforts should be centered around alleviating poverty and improving access to necessities. This approach reflected his commitment to transforming the socio-economic landscape of Nepal by focusing on the needs of its most vulnerable populations (Nepal

Gazette, 1959, November 2). By implementing these targeted development strategies, Koirala sought to rectify the inequities inherited from the previous regime and lay the foundation for a more equitable and inclusive society. His administration's emphasis on addressing the needs of the rural poor marked a significant departure from the practices of the past and aimed to foster meaningful improvements in the quality of life for Nepal's most disadvantaged citizens.

Campaign to Open Primary Schools

Prior to 2007, Nepal's educational system was starkly limited and heavily skewed towards serving the elite. The country had only a small number of high schools and primary schools, with educational resources primarily concentrated in urban areas (Shreshtha, 2014). This distribution meant that access to quality education was largely restricted to a privileged few, leaving a vast majority of the population with minimal educational opportunities. Recognizing the critical need for educational reform, the elected government undertook significant measures to address these disparities. A major component of this initiative was the substantial increase in the education budget, which aimed to expand access to education across the country. In addition to boosting financial resources, the government launched an ambitious plan to establish new educational institutions in underserved areas. One of the key strategies implemented was the opening of 15 primary schools per constituency. This initiative was designed to bring education closer to rural and remote communities, thereby reducing the gap between urban and rural educational facilities. The goal was to ensure that even the most isolated regions had access to basic education, thereby promoting greater equity in educational opportunities. By 1960, these efforts had resulted in a significant expansion of the country's educational infrastructure. The total number of schools in Nepal increased dramatically, reaching 2,508. This figure included 1,624 newly established schools that were part of the government's concerted effort to enhance educational access and quality across the nation (Mahat, Desh Snachar, 2020, October

4). The creation of these new schools marked a pivotal shift in Nepal's educational landscape, demonstrating a commitment to inclusive education and the provision of learning opportunities for all children, regardless of their geographic location.

The expansion of the educational system not only provided more schools but also contributed to a broader goal of improving educational outcomes and fostering long-term development. By increasing the availability of primary schools in various constituencies, the government aimed to empower more children with the foundational knowledge and skills needed for personal and societal advancement. Overall, the period leading up to and including 2060 witnessed a transformative change in Nepal's approach to education. The government's efforts to enhance educational access and infrastructure represented a critical step towards addressing historical inequities and laying the groundwork for a more inclusive and equitable educational system.

Health Post

In pre-democratic Nepal, public health was severely underdeveloped, with healthcare access being a significant challenge. The country had only a handful of hospitals and health centers, leaving a vast majority of the population with limited or no access to medical services. This lack of infrastructure and resources contributed to poor health outcomes and a general absence of comprehensive healthcare. Recognizing the dire need for improvement, the first five-year plan implemented after the establishment of democratic governance made public health a central focus. The plan aimed to address the critical deficiencies in the healthcare system and lay the foundation for a more robust health infrastructure. A major component of this strategy was the expansion of healthcare facilities across the country. This included not only increasing the number of hospitals and clinics but also ensuring that these facilities were accessible to people in rural and remote areas, where healthcare was particularly scarce.

In addition to expanding healthcare infrastructure, the first five-year plan placed a

significant emphasis on improving public health through the provision of clean drinking water. Access to safe water is fundamental to preventing waterborne diseases and promoting overall health, and the plan recognized this as a crucial element in enhancing public health. Substantial investments were directed towards these goals, reflecting a commitment to transforming the public health landscape. The increased funding and focus on healthcare infrastructure and clean water were intended to improve health outcomes and address long-standing deficiencies in the system. By investing in these areas, the government aimed to ensure that all citizens, regardless of their location, could access essential health services and benefit from improved sanitary conditions. Overall, the first five-year plan marked a pivotal step towards modernizing Nepal's public health system. The emphasis on expanding healthcare facilities and providing clean drinking water represented a critical effort to overcome the challenges of the past and build a healthier future for the nation (Proceedings of the House of Representatives, July 30, 1960).

Expansion of Road Transport Services

During the Rana era, Nepal's infrastructure was severely underdeveloped, with no paved roads available. This lack of modern road infrastructure significantly hindered transportation and connectivity within the country. However, the post-democratic period marked a dramatic shift in this regard, as the government prioritized the expansion and improvement of road infrastructure. One of the major achievements of the post-democratic government was the substantial increase in motorable and paved roads. This development aimed to enhance connectivity between various regions of Nepal, facilitating easier movement of people and goods. The expansion of road networks played a crucial role in promoting economic growth and improving access to services and resources across the country. Significant infrastructure projects were launched to support this transformation. Among these was the ambitious east-west highway project, which aimed to create a continuous, well-paved road stretching across the length of Nepal. This

highway was designed to bridge the gap between the eastern and western parts of the country, making transportation more efficient and linking remote areas with major urban centers.

In addition to the east-west highway, efforts were made to improve overall transport services. The enhancement of road infrastructure was complemented by upgrades to transport facilities, ensuring that the roads could effectively support increased traffic and provide reliable service to users. Overall, the post-democratic era marked a period of significant progress in road infrastructure development. The establishment of paved roads and major projects like the east-west highway represented a commitment to modernizing Nepal's transport network, thereby fostering economic development and improving the quality of life for its citizens (Poudel, Shilapatra, 2023, September 10).

Emphasis on the Development of Journalism

Before 2007, Nepal's media landscape was notably underdeveloped, characterized by a limited number of publications and low circulation rates. The media sector faced significant challenges, including restricted access to resources and a lack of support for journalism. The first elected government recognized the critical role of a free and robust media in a democratic society and took proactive measures to address these issues. One of their key initiatives was to categorize newspapers, which helped streamline the media landscape and improve the organization of print media. This categorization aimed to better manage the diverse range of publications and facilitate more effective media operations (Nepal, 2023).

In addition to categorization, the government introduced policies to support and sustain the media industry. A major step in this direction was the provision of government advertisements to newspapers. This support was intended to boost the financial stability of media outlets, helping them to expand their reach and improve their quality of journalism. By allocating government advertisements, the administration provided a vital source of revenue for

newspapers, which in turn contributed to the growth and development of the media sector. These measures marked a significant shift in the government's approach to media development. The support for journalism and media infrastructure helped lay the foundation for a more vibrant and dynamic media landscape in Nepal. The improved support for newspapers and the structured approach to media categorization were crucial in enhancing the role of journalism in the country, promoting greater access to information, and fostering a more informed public (Birahi, 2004).

Balanced Foreign Policy with Neighbors

During BP Koirala's tenure as Prime Minister of Nepal, he aimed to foster strong relationships with both neighboring countries, China and India. His strategy was to ensure that Nepal could receive support from both nations. In this context, Nepal sought assistance from China, which responded positively, providing aid to Nepal. However, India perceived this move as an affront, interpreting it as a slight against both Nepal and it. The diplomatic tension led to a public backlash, and amid the controversy, Prime Minister Koirala retracted his earlier statement in Parliament. This incident highlighted the delicate balance Koirala had to maintain in navigating Nepal's foreign relations with its two significant neighbors (Koirala, 2010).

After a period of escalating tensions over the issue, Nepal formally lodged a protest regarding the situation. This diplomatic disagreement stemmed from a controversy involving India's reaction to Nepal's request for assistance from China. Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, who had initially made a statement that was perceived as disparaging towards both Nepal and China, faced significant backlash. The Indian government's response to Nepal's protest was swift. Considering the diplomatic strain and the need to maintain positive relations with its neighbor, Nehru took the step of retracting his earlier statement in Parliament. This retraction was a crucial move to ease the diplomatic friction between the two countries and to address Nepal's concerns. By publicly withdrawing his

remarks, Nehru aimed to mitigate the damage to bilateral relations and reaffirm India's commitment to fostering a harmonious relationship with Nepal. This incident underscored the complexities of international diplomacy and the importance of careful communication in managing relations between neighboring states (Devkota, 1980).

During Koirala's tenure, maintaining balanced relations with both India and China was a central diplomatic priority. Koirala undertook diplomatic visits to both countries to enhance Nepal's international standing and secure vital support. These visits proved instrumental in fostering stronger ties, leading to substantial aid and beneficial agreements for Nepal (Dahal BBC 18 October 2023). Despite facing challenges, including a diplomatic incident with China, Koirala's approach to foreign diplomacy yielded significant advancements. The incident posed difficulties, yet Koirala's adept handling of such issues and his commitment to nurturing Nepal's relations with major neighboring countries ensured continued progress in foreign diplomacy (Pandey, 2016). Koirala's diplomatic efforts were characterized by a strategic balancing act, aiming to leverage Nepal's relationships with both India and China to bolster the country's development and secure essential resources. His tenure thus marked a period of notable achievements in foreign relations, reflecting his skillful navigation of complex international dynamics (Acharya, 2014).

Conclusion

King Mahendra's dissolution of the first elected government, despite its significant strides in governance and reform, was a notable setback for democracy in Nepal. The short-lived tenure of Bishweshwar Prasad Koirala's administration—lasting just 18 months—represented a fleeting but impactful chapter in Nepalese political history. During this brief period, Koirala's government undertook transformative initiatives across various sectors. In governance, Koirala's administration implemented pioneering measures such as

reducing the salaries of high-ranking officials and slashing the expenses of the Prime Minister's Office. These actions were symbolic of a commitment to addressing the socio-economic challenges facing Nepal, reflecting a deeper dedication to public service and equity. Additionally, the government worked diligently on land reforms, ending the feudal Birta system and granting legal rights to farmers, which marked a significant shift in land ownership and agricultural policy. The administration's impact extended to social reforms and infrastructure development. Koirala's emphasis on education saw the expansion of schools, increasing access to education across the country. His efforts in public health aimed to improve healthcare facilities and access, addressing a critical need in a country previously underserved in this sector. Furthermore, Koirala's focus on infrastructure, including road construction and transport improvements, began laying the groundwork for future development. In foreign relations, Koirala's balanced diplomatic approach with India and China was crucial in securing aid and strengthening Nepal's international position. His diplomatic visits and negotiations played a key role in fostering beneficial agreements despite facing challenges, including a diplomatic incident with China. Ultimately, while King Mahendra's actions curtailed the immediate advancement of democratic governance, the legacy of Koirala's brief tenure endures in the form of lasting impacts on governance, social reform, and foreign relations. His commitment to democratic ideals and public service continues to inspire and reflect a significant chapter in Nepalese political history.

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